

Studies in Thiazolo Quinoxalines. Part I

Simran Singh, Harjit Singh, R. S. Narang, Sardul Singh and M. L. Mahajan

2-Arylimino-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo(4,5-b)quinoxalines and 2-imino-3-aryl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxalines have been obtained by the condensation of 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines and N-aryl thioureas. N-phenyl-N'-methyl thiourea on interaction with the dichloro quinoxaline furnished 2-phenylimino-3-methyl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo(4,5-b)quinoxaline and 2-methyl-imino-3-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b)quinoxaline.

Thiazolo quinoxalines (I) were first synthesised by Saikachi and Tagami¹ through the condensation of 2-mercapto-3-amino quinoxaline and acid halides or anhydrides. We report here the synthesis of various 2,3-substituted-2 : 3-dihydro derivatives of (I) by condensing 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines (II) with thiourea derivatives. The following probable course depicts the formation of 2-arylimino-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b)quinoxalines (III) and 2-imino-3-aryl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxalines (IV) (Table I).

The separation of the two products formed in each case could be easily accomplished through their wide difference in solubilities. One of these products, the major one, was usually less soluble in alcohol and separated during reactions carried out in ethanolic solution, whereas the isomeric minor component, more often preferred to remain in solution. The former have been assigned the structure III as on hydrolysis with conc. sulphuric acid or ethanolic potassium hydroxide they ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$, $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$, $p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$ and $o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$) furnished the same product 2-keto-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b)

1. S. Haruo and Shoichiro Tagami, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* (Tokyo), 1961, 9, 41; *Chem. Abstr.*, 57, 16614.

quinoxaline (VI) by knocking off the arylimino substituent from position 2. However, IV ($\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$) on similar treatment gave ammonia and V ($\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$). Again N-methyl-N'-phenyl thiourea on condensation with II in ethanol furnished the less soluble (III), ($\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_3 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) and more soluble (IV) ($\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{CH}_3$, $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$). The former on hydrolysis furnished aniline and 2-keto-3-methyl-2 : 3-dihydrothiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxaline (VI) ($\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{CH}_3$) whereas the latter gave V ($\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$).

6 : 7-Disubstituted-2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines (II), likewise furnished corresponding III and IV. But the presence of different groups at positions 6 or 7 in quinoxaline through electronic effects make the chlorine at 2 and 3 positions, reactive to different extents². The more reactive chlorine, through preferred reaction with the thiol group will guide the reaction. The presence of chlorine and methyl at position 6 (II, $\text{R}_1 = \text{Cl}$ and CH_3 , $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$) through electron release will deactivate the chlorine at position 2 and consequently the two products formed on condensation with various thioureas are III and IV ($\text{R}_1 = \text{Cl}$, CH_3 and $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$). But the presence of nitro at position 7 (II, $\text{R}_2 = \text{NO}_2$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$) by electron withdrawal will make the chlorine at position 3 more labile and consequently furnish III and IV ($\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{NO}_2$).

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Condensation of 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines with N-aryl thioureas and N-phenyl-N'-methyl thioureas.

General Procedure .

(a) Equivalent amounts of II and aryl thioureas were refluxed in ethanolic solution. Separation of the solid product (III, $\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$) started after refluxing for 20–40 minutes. Reaction of 2 : 3-dichloro-6-methyl quinoxaline with phenyl thiourea was relatively slow and the separation of the solid started after refluxing for 1 hr. The reaction mixtures were refluxed for 3 hrs for the completion of the reactions and the solids separated were filtered, washed with sodium carbonate solution and water and crystallised from acetic acid as greenish needles. The residues obtained after distilling off the solvent from the mother liquor were washed with aqueous sodium carbonate solution and water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish the minor component (IV, $\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$).

(b) Alternatively these condensations were carried out by heating the reaction mixtures at 140–50° for 2 hrs in solid state. After trituration with aqueous sodium carbonate solution the products were washed with water and were repeatedly extracted with hot ethanol. The ethanolic extract furnished brown solids IV, ($\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$) whereas residues were found to be III ($\text{R}_3 = \text{H}$). First method gave better yields and was used in these reactions.

Condensation of N-methyl-N'-phenyl thiourea with II was carried out in ethanolic solution and the two products namely, 2-phenyl imino-3-methyl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazole quinoxaline (III, $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{CH}_3$), m.p. 265° (Found C, 65.88; H, 4.12, N, 18.95. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 65.75; H, 4.69; N, 19.17) and 2-methylimino-3-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro

thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxaline (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = H$; Ar = C_6H_5 ; $R_3 = CH_3$) m.p. 190° , (Found : C, 65.61; H, 4.61; N, 18.86 : $C_{16}H_{12}N_4S$ requires C, 65.75; H, 4.09; N, 19.17%).

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Product formed			m.p. $^\circ C$		Yield %		Molecular formula		Analytical results**		
	R_1	R_2	Ar	III	IV	III	IV			Found % III*	IV	Reqd. %
1.	H	H	$-C_6H_5$	302	150	55	25	$C_{15}H_{10}N_4S$	N,	19.85	19.90	20.14
2.	H	H	$p-C_6H_4Cl$	295	300	50	25	$C_{15}H_9ClN_4S$	C,	57.34		57.69
									H,	2.52		2.88
									N,	18.18	17.64	17.92
3.	H	H	$p-C_6H_4CH_3$	272	215	45	20	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4S$	N,	18.80	19.90	19.17
4.	H	H	$p-C_6H_4OC_2H_5$	270	200	40	22	$C_{17}H_{14}N_4SO$	N,	16.92	17.10	17.39
5.	H	H	$p-C_6H_4Cl$	267	198	45	20	$C_{15}H_9ClN_4S$	N,	17.49	17.63	17.92
6.	H	H	$p-C_6H_4COOH$	335	210	50	22	$C_{16}H_{10}N_4SO_2$	N,	17.48	17.21	17.39
7.	H	H	$p-C_6H_4COOC_2H_5$	314	185	52	20	$C_{18}H_{14}N_4SO_2$	N,	15.64	15.22	16.00
8.	H	NO_2	$p-C_6H_4Cl$	235	180	50	20	$C_{15}H_8ClN_5SO_2$	S,	8.49	8.73	8.96
9.	H	NO_2	$p-C_6H_4Br$	245	250	50	22	$C_{15}H_8BrN_5SO_2$	N,	17.78	17.74	17.41
10.	H	NO_2	$o-C_6H_4OCH_3$	268	150	40	20	$C_{16}H_{11}N_5SO_3$	S,	8.64	8.59	9.07
11.	H	NO_2	$o-C_6H_4OC_2H_5$	240	165	40	25	$C_{17}H_{13}N_5SO_3$	S,	8.52	8.40	8.72
12.	Cl	H	$p-C_6H_4Cl$	295	200	45	22	$C_{15}H_8Cl_2N_4S$	N,	15.82	15.72	16.13
13.	Cl	H	C_6H_5	265	200	45	20	$C_{15}H_9ClN_4S$	N,	17.95	17.70	17.92
14.	Cl	H	$o-C_6H_4OCH_3$	250	195	50	25	$C_{16}H_{11}ClN_4SO$	N,	16.48	16.30	16.37
15.	CH_3	H	C_6H_5	285	202	40	20	$C_{16}H_{12}N_4S$	N,	19.07	19.04	19.17
16.	CH_3	H	$p-C_6H_4COOC_2H_5$	225	185	42	20	$C_{19}H_{16}N_4SO_2$	N,	15.20	14.97	15.38
17.	CH_3	CH_3	C_6H_5	280	212	45	20	$C_{17}H_{14}N_4S$	N,	18.05	18.20	18.30

* III were crystallised from acetic acid whereas for the crystallisation of IV, ethanol was used.

** Analytical results are by M/s B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar of Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh.

2. *Hydrolysis of 2-arylimino-2:3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b)quinoxaline (III, $R_3 = H$); Formation of VI ($R_3 = H$)*

(a) *With ethanolic potassium hydroxide* : III ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, Ar = C_6H_5) (2 g.) was refluxed in ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution (30 ml., 5%) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, the product separated, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 230° . (Found : N, 20.23. $C_9H_5N_3SO$ requires N, 20.68%). III ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$; Ar = $p-C_6H_4CH_3$) on similar hydrolysis furnished VI ($R_3 = H$) found to be identical with the product obtained above through undepressed mixed melting point.

(b) *With conc. sulphuric acid* : III ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, Ar = $p-C_6H_4Cl$) (2 g.) was dissolved in minimum amount of dioxan and conc. sulphuric acid (2 ml.) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. It was cooled, diluted with water and the product (VI, $R_3 = H$) separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. It melted at 228° and did not depress the melting point when mixed with the authentic sample.

Similarly III ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $Ar = o-C_6H_4CH_3$) on hydrolysis also furnished VI ($R_3 = H$).

For the hydrolysis of 2-phenylimino-3-methyl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b)quinoxaline (III, $R_1 = R_2 = H$, $R_3 = CH_3$; $Ar = C_6H_5$) with ethanolic potassium hydroxide (2 g.) of the compound was refluxed with ethanolic potassium hydroxide (30 ml., 5%) on water bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish VI ($R_3 = CH_3$), m.p. 300°. (Found : N, 19.14%, $C_{10}H_7N_3SO$ requires N, 19.36%).

3. *Hydrolysis of 2-imino-3-phenyl-2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxaline (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$) with ethanolic potassium hydroxide.*

IV ($R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$, $Ar = C_6H_5$) (2 g.) was refluxed with ethanolic KOH (30 ml., 5%) till ammonia gas ceased to evolve. It was cooled and the product separated was crystallised from ethanol m.p., 210°, (Found : N, 15.25%; $C_{15}H_9N_3SO$ requires N, 15.05%).

Hydrolysis of 2-methylimino-3-phenyl 2 : 3-dihydro thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxaline (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = H$, $R_3 = CH_3$, $Ar = C_6H_5$) was carried out with conc. sulphuric acid as in expt. 2b to furnish V ($R_1 = R_2 = H$, $Ar = C_6H_5$) m.p. 210° which was found to be identical with the product obtained in expt. 3 above as determined by its undepressed mixed melting point.

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. S. Narang for his helpful suggestions and one of the authors (S.S.) is thankful to C.S.I.R. for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

Department of Chemistry,
Panjab University,
Chandigarh.

Received April 7, 1969
Revised MSS received March 30, 1970